

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "EFFECTS OF PLYOMETRIC TRAINING TO IMPROVE PERFORMANCE IN PROFESSIONAL SOCCER PLAYERS" is a bonafide project work done by ANSARI NIKHAT PARVEEN MOHD MUSTAFA under the guidance of Assistant Prof Dr VIDHYA KRISHNA P Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 23/3/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr.S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
S. Rajasekar
Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "**Physiotherapy Management in Cervicogenic Headache-A Literature Review**" is a bonafide project work done by **ANTISHREE M G** under the guidance of **Asst.Prof Dr. HARSHA M NAIK** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date:

9/03/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean:

Prof. Dr. S. RAJASEKAR

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean

Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus

Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled “**MOTOR CONTROL TRAINING IN PATIENT SUFFERING FROM KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS**” is a bonafide project work done by **ASHVITHA** under the guidance of Assistant professor **Dr. PATHAK ANUPAMA ANAND** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 30/03/22
Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project titled “A LITERATURE REVIEW ON PSYCHOSOMATIC ASPECTS OF LOW BACK PAIN” is a bonafide project work done by NAYANA SRINIVAS CHODE under the guidance of Assistant professor SANYA A.Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date:

31/03/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "TEXT NECK SYNDROME CAUSED BY SMARTPHONES: EFFICACY OF CONVENTIONAL EXERCISE PROGRAM AND OCULAR MUSCLE RETRAINING-A REVIEW OF LITERATURE" is a bonafied project work done by MANJU VIJAYKUMAR CHORDIYA under the guidance of Assistant Prof Dr. Tamilalagan M. Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 31/3/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

DR.S.RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Mangalore

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "The Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool (CAIT) v/s The Foot and Ankle Ability Measure (FAAM) in diagnosis of patients with chronic ankle instability – A Literature Review." is a bonafide project work done by HARSH JITENDRA RAVAL under the guidance of Assistant Prof Dr. CAROLIN MENEZES Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date:

29/3/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy

Dean

Institute of Physiotherapy

Srinivas University

Srinivas Campus

Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "**EFFECTIVENESS OF LSVT- BIG IN PARKINSONS DISEASE FOR IMPROVING MOVEMENT- A LITERATURE REVIEW**" is a bonafide project work done by **HARSHITHA** under the guidance of **Asst.Prof Dr. MADHURIPU P** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 24 - 03 - 2022

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean:

Prof. Dr. S. RAJASEKAR

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "EFFECT OF VIRTUAL REALITY ON ADULTS WITH MILD COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT, PREVENTING DEMENTIA-A LITERATURE REVIEW" is a bonafide project work done by **HELAN MARIA SHAJI** under the guidance of Assistant Prof **Dr PRAJNA RAO** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 29/03/22
Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Department of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "A LITERATURE REVIEW ON MANAGEMENT OF FATIGUE IN MOTOR NEURON DISEASE" is a bonafide project work done by JESLIN under the guidance of Dr PATHAK ANUPAMA ANAND Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date:

29/03/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr.S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean

Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled “EFFECTS OF PHYSIOTHERAPY ON QUANTITY OF LIFE AFTER CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFT (CABG)” is a bonafide project work done by PRIYANKA NAGESH KALSHETTY under the guidance of Assistant Prof **DR. VISHAGH NAIR** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 04/04/22
Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

DR. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Bandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "**PREVALENCE OF POST COVID DIABETES MELLITUS AND THEIR QUALITY OF LIFE - A SURVEY BASED STUDY**" is a bonafide project work done by **KUNJAL VINOD KAMERKAR** under the guidance of Assistant Prof **Dr. TAMILALAGAN M.Srinivas** University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date:

29/03/22

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that project entitled **OCCURRENCE OF FORWARD HEAD POSTURE DUE TO POOR POSTURE AND ERGONOMICS** is a bonafied project work done by **MAHI RAKESH KAPADIA** under the guidance of Assisant professor **Dr SANYA A.Srinivas** University of Physiotherapy, Manglore.

Date : 31 / 03 / 22
Place : Manglore

signature of the dean

Dr. RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR AND DEAN

Srinivas University college of Physiotheapry

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "A LITERATURE REVIEW ON EFFECT OF TRANSVERSE ABDOMINIS STRENGTHENING IN DIASTASIS RECTI" is a bonafide project work done by **RIA UMESH KARKERA** under the guidance of Assistant Prof **DR. RADHIKA GOPAL**, Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 28/3/22

Place: MANGALORE

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

and Research Centre

Dean

Institute of Physiotherapy

Srinivas University

Srinivas Campus

Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "**MIRROR THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PHANTOM LIMB PAIN AMONG THE UPPER LIMB AMPUTEES PATIENTS : SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**" is a bonafide project work done by **SATHEESHA KUMAR K** under the guidance of Assistant Prof **Dr AISHWARYA NITIN SONWANE** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: *25/05/2022*

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean:

Prof. Dr.S .RAJASHEKAR

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Sri Jayachamarajendra
Pandeshwar, Mysore-575 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "A LITERATURE REVIEW ON ROLE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY IN A WOMEN WITH BREAST CANCER" is a bonafide project work done by **SHAHANA SHIRIN C H** under the guidance of Associate Prof **Dr THRISHALA NORONHA** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 10/03/22
Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr.S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 576 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "" **Ballon Blowing exercise in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)** "" -A literature review"" is a bonafide project work done by **SHEETAL** under the guidance. Of Asst Prof Dr. **JEYAGANESH VELLASAMY** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, *Mangalore*.

Date: 09/03/22
Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean:

Prof. Dr. S RAJASEKAR

Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy

Dean,
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 578 001

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the project entitled "**PHYSIOTHERAPY MANAGEMENT FOR LOW-BIRTH-WEIGHT INFANT**" is a bonafide project work done by **SUPRIYA G** under the guidance of Assistant Prof **Dr PALLAVI ANNA MATHEW** Srinivas University College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore.

Date: 24/03/2022

Place: Mangalore

Signature of the Dean

Dr. S RAJASEKAR

PROFESSOR and DEAN

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